

**A STUDY ON CONSUMERS AWARENESS TOWARDS
ORGANIC FOOD PRODUCTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE
TO TIRUPUR DISTRICT**

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Abstract:

In today's world organic food products was very important for the human beings to lead a healthy life. have become a basic necessity in human life. In this paper, an attempt has been made to find out the consumers awareness towards organic food. A sample of 100 respondents' was purposively selected from Tirupur District. The selected samples are analyzed using simple percentage, chi-square test and multiple regression analysis test. It is found that three variables namely there exists any significant association between gender, age, educational qualification, monthly income and consumer awareness towards organic food products of the respondents.

Key Words: Consumer, Awareness, Organic Food, Vegetables, Fruits & Health

Introduction:

Organic food refers to food items that are prepared and processed without using any chemicals. Organic livestock raised for meat, eggs, and dairy products must have access to the outdoors and be given organic feed. Organic foods have been proven to contain 50 per cent more vitamins, minerals and nutrients than similar food that is produced in regular manner. Organic food is healthier than conventional food is quite strong, and is the main reason for increase in its demand in its demand over the past 5-6 years. Organic foods often have more beneficial nutrients, such as antioxidants, than their conventionally-grown counterparts and people with allergies to foods, chemicals, or preservatives often find their symptoms lessen or go away when they eat only organic foods.

Organic food is fresher because it doesn't contain preservatives that make it last longer. Organic farming is better for the environment. Organic farming practices reduce pollution, conserve water, reduce soil erosion, increase soil fertility, and use less energy. Organically raised animals are NOT given antibiotics, growth hormones, or fed animal by products. Organic farmers are on the cutting edge of science as they are focused on finding ways to produce quality foods without the use of the chemicals that are harmful to our health, and the health of the planet. These farmers have used innovative techniques to replace the chemicals that can be so damaging, and do their research using their own funding at their own farms. Natural fertilizers, like manure, work perfectly fine, and organic farmers are happy to use this smellier, yet safer, form of fertilizer.

Review of Literature:

Sathyendra Kumar AD and Dr. H. M. Chandrashekar (2015) revealed that an attempt to understanding the consumer perception about organic product and marketing in Mysore city. Primary data are collected from Retail outlets of Organic products, Organic Products Marketing Agencies, by administering the structured questionnaires through simple random sampling method. Parentage analysis and SPSS will be adopted to analysis the consumer's response towards organic food product in Mysore city. The results concluded that most of the consumer especially in urban people prefer organic food product.

J. Padmathy and R. Saraswathy (2016) investigated the relationship between variables that affect consumers' buying behaviour for organic products and identifies the price levels consumers prefer to pay for organic products in Thanjavur district. Convenience sampling method was used to select 200 respondents living in the district and who make purchases for the products. The primary data was collected from the respondents with questionnaires. The statistical method used for the study as regression and chi-square analyzes. The findings of the study reveal that there is significant relationship between the variables which affects consumers' buying behaviour for organic products.

Md Tareq Bin Hossain and Pei Xian Lim (2016) evaluated the current status of consumers' buying behavior towards organic foods in the emerging market. A well structured questionnaire was designed and distributed to around 105 respondents randomly in Malaysia (Penang). The data collected are analysed using SPSS software with version 21.0 The study found that government support and policy, perceived beliefs and attitudes, knowledge and availability have a significant positive relationship with consumer behavior towards organic foods.

Statement of the Problem:

People are very sensitive to their health issues, and they often take precautions to make sure they remain healthy, like getting various vaccines and taking antibiotics as soon as a new strain of bacteria makes them ill. However, non-organic food sources, particularly livestock and feed houses, also use antibiotics to feed

their animals. This extra dose of antibiotics may actually be weakening our immune system by basically overdosing on antibiotics, thereby reshaping our immune system so many times that it will eventually be unable to defend itself. Organic food growers and dairy farmers do not use antibiotics in their processes. Since organic food is not prepared using chemical fertilizers, it does not contain any traces of these strong chemicals and might not affect the human body in negative ways. In this context it is very important to know the consumer awareness towards Organic Food Products.

Objectives of the Study:

To determine the consumers awareness towards Organic foods with special reference to Tirupur district.

Research Methodology:

Area of Study: Tirupur District

Data: Both Primary and Secondary data have been collected for this study. Primary data have collected through Questionnaire and secondary data have been collected through various journals, articles, magazines, etc.,

Sample Size: 100

Sampling Method: Purposive sampling

Statistical Tools:

- ✓ Simple Percentage
- ✓ Chi-Square Test
- ✓ Multiple Regression Analysis

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is restricted to the selected sample of Tirupur District and hence the result of the study cannot be generalized.
- ✓ The statistical methods used to analyze the data have their own limitation.
- ✓ All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Factors	Number of Respondents N=100	Percentage
Gender		
Male	24	24
Female	76	76
Age (Years)		
Up to 25	26	26
26 to 50	47	47
Above 50	17	17
Educational Qualification		
Up to School Level	35	35
Graduate	37	37
Professional	28	28
Occupation		
Agriculture	18	18
Employee	19	19
Professional	24	24
Business	13	13
House Wife	26	26
Monthly Income		
Up to Rs.10000	35	35
Rs.10000 to Rs.25000	48	48
Above Rs.25000	17	17
Type of Family		
Joint Family	45	45
Nuclear Family	55	55
Information about Organic food		
Family	23	23
Social Media	25	25
Friends	17	17
Doctors/ Professionals	35	35
Place of Shopping		
Market	35	35
Departmental Stores	29	29

Organic food Shop	46	46
Reasons to Buy		
Harmless	34	34
Healthy	36	36
Natural	30	30
Frequency of Buying		
Daily	27	27
Weekly	43	43
Monthly	30	30
Products Purchased		
Organic Vegetables and Fruits	45	45
Milk and Milk Products	20	20
Cereals and Pulses	25	25
Other Organic Food	10	10

Demographic Profile of the Respondents:

Table 1 describes the demographic profile of the rural consumers towards ORGANIC FOOD are taken for the study. Out of 100 respondents who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (76%) of the respondents are female, (47%) whose age group is under 26 to 50 years, most (37%) of the respondents are graduates, maximum number (26%) of respondents are house wife, the monthly income of (48%) respondents is Rs.10,001 to Rs.25,000, (55%) respondents have nuclear family, (35%) of respondents came to know about Organic foods through doctors or professionals, (46%) of respondents buy their Organic food in specialized Organic food shop, majority (36%) of respondents buy Organic food due of healthy reasons, (43%) of the respondents purchase their Organic food weekly and (45%) of respondents purchase organic foods and vegetables.

Table 2: Relationship between Demographic Profile and Consumer awareness towards organic food Products of the Respondents

Variables	χ^2 Value	Table Value	S/NS
Gender	7.534	5.991	S
Age	12.596	9.488	S
Educational Qualification	14.178	9.488	S
Occupation	16.515	15.507	NS
Type of Family	4.135	5.991	NS
Monthly Income	12.765	9.488	S

*significant at 5% percent level

Relationship between Demographic Profile and Consumer awareness towards organic food Products of the Respondents:

Table 3 depicts the relationship between selected demographic variables and the consumer awareness towards organic food products of the respondents. It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is greater than the table value at five percent level, there exists any significant association between gender, age, educational qualification, monthly income and consumer awareness towards organic food products of the respondents. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected. It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is less than the table value at five percent level, there exists no significant association between occupation, type of family and consumer awareness towards organic food products of the respondents. Thus the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 3: Determinants of Consumer Awareness towards Organic Food Products-Multiple Regression Analysis

Factors	Regression Coefficient	Standard Error	T
Gender	3.308*	1.609	2.056
Age	1.305	0.945	1.381
Educational Qualification	0.330*	0.065	5.059
Occupation	0.044	0.618	0.071
Type of Family	0.438	1.938	0.226
Monthly Income	4.269*	1.848	2.31

* five per cent level

- ✓ **Gender:** Table 3 reveals that gender highly influences awareness. The value of regression co-efficient indicates that a unit of increase in monthly income shall increase awareness by 0.001 units. Female consumer leads to higher level of awareness at five percent level of significance.
- ✓ **Educational Qualification:** The multiple regression co-efficient indicate that consumers education highly influences the level of awareness. The value of regression coefficient indicates that a unit of increase in level of education will increase the awareness by 0.330 units.

- ✓ **Monthly Income:** The table reveals that monthly income positively influences the level of awareness. The value of regression co-efficient indicates that a unit of increase in monthly income shall increase awareness by 4.269 units. Higher amount of monthly income leads to higher level of awareness at five percent level of significance.

Findings of the Study:

- ✓ Majority of the consumers are female.
- ✓ Majority of the consumers age is between 26 to 50 years.
- ✓ Majority of the consumers are house wife
- ✓ Most of the consumers are graduates.
- ✓ Using Chi-square it is found that there exists any significant association between gender, age, educational qualification, monthly income and consumer awareness towards organic food products of the respondents
- ✓ Using multiple regression analysis, it is found that gender, educational qualification and monthly income have an association with consumers awareness towards organic food.

Conclusion:

Organic food is one of the most oldest, widely accepted, highly appreciated organic farming. It should reach each and every man for their health. There is a need for educating the consumers and awareness about organic goods. Government, agriculturist, health organization should take necessary steps to make awareness about organic food products. There is huge gap between the agriculture and consumer awareness. This gap can be removed through two methods one is giving awareness about the organic food product and another is educating them about organic farming. The research concludes that consumer awareness plays a vital role in determining the buying behavioral aspect for selecting organic food.

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